

Supplementary material

Efficient methodology for the extraction and analysis of lipids from porcine pulmonary artery by supercritical fluid chromatography coupled to mass spectrometry

Alicia Gil-Ramirez^{a,*}, Said Al-Hamimi^a, Oskar Rosmark^b, Oskar Hallgren^{b,c}, Anna-Karin Larsson-Callerfelt^b, Irene Rodríguez-Meizoso^{a,*}

^aCentre for Analysis and Synthesis, Department of Chemistry, Lund University, SE-22100, Lund, Sweden

^bLung Biology, Department of Experimental Medical Science, Faculty of Medicine, Lund University, SE-22184, Lund, Sweden

^cDepartment of Respiratory Medicine and Allergology, Lund University, Sweden

***Corresponding author.**

E-mail addresses: aliciagilramirez@gmail.com/ irenerome@icloud.com

Tables

Table S1. Matrix effect comparison between MA-C, ME and MF per lipid class expressed as percentage. * $p < 0.05$ between the areas of the corresponding ISs in samples and the IS area in $\text{CHCl}_3:\text{MeOH}$ (1:1, v/v) obtained from the analysis of the variance (ANOVA), followed by Tukey's test.

Extraction method	ME per lipid class (%)				
	TGs	PCs	SMs	MGs	FAs
MA	$60.7 \pm 26.7^*$	88.8 ± 26.5	86.26 ± 14.6	89.0 ± 16.0	78.1 ± 12.7
MB	74.6 ± 13.4	104.8 ± 17.6	88.6 ± 10.5	101.5 ± 31.4	82.9 ± 13.8
MC	82.2 ± 24.7	110.3 ± 29.2	94.1 ± 15.5	97.1 ± 9.5	$65.3 \pm 20.8^*$
ME	78.7 ± 15.0	92.56 ± 15.6	95.4 ± 8.1	97.6 ± 7.1	88.3 ± 25.6
MF	83.0 ± 13.4	84.0 ± 194	$77.8 \pm 8.9^*$	84.6 ± 10.0	77.0 ± 11.6

Figures

Fig. S1. Influence of the number of double bonds (A) and the length (B) of the fatty acyl chains in the elution times of PCs.

Fig. S2. UHPSFC/QTOF-MS chromatograms of the extracted ions of MG 18:0 in positive mode (A) and FA 18:0 in negative mode (B) resulted from MG fragmentation (sample from Method A, MA). The spectra obtained from the centred area of the peak was included for both compounds (framed area).

Fig. S3. Relative quantification of SMs species in MA, MB and ME expressed as normalized area per mg of dried tissue. Data are expressed as means $\pm$ SD; n=6 for MA-B and n=5 for ME.